

LOCAL HEALTH COUNCILS AS A POSSIBILITY OF EFFECTIVE SOCIAL CONTROL: EXPERIENCE REPORT IN A MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESIDENCY IN FAMILY HEALTH

LOS CONSEJOS LOCALES DE SALUD COMO POSIBILIDAD DE REALIZAR EL CONTROL SOCIAL: REPORTE DE EXPERIENCIA EN UNA RESIDENCIA MULTIPROFESIONAL EN SALUD FAMILIAR

CONSELHOS LOCAIS DE SAÚDE COMO POSSIBILIDADE DE EFETIVAÇÃO DO CONTROLE SOCIAL: RELATO DE EXPERIÊNCIA EM UMA RESIDÊNCIA MULTIPROFISSIONAL EM SAÚDE DA FAMÍLIA

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Abstract

A social control in health constitutes an institutional mechanism for community participation in the formulation and implementation of public health policies in Brazil. Local Health Councils (LHC) could be important instruments to support municipal management and the decentralization process of Unified Health System (SUS). This work aimed to report the experience lived, between 2023 and 2024, by residents of a Multidisciplinary Residency in Family Health in the process of reactivating the LHC of a family health unit, located in a municipality in the interior of Bahia. This is a descriptive study, of the experience report type. The actions carried out, organized through situational diagnosis, raised by strategic planning, provided conditions for dialogue about social control and popular participation, acting as drivers for the establishment of debate and problematization of the work process in basic health care, in

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addition to facilitating the reestablishment of LHC in the municipality, mobilizing users and community, activated workers on teams and service managers.

Keywords: Primary Health Care; Social control; Health Councils; Community Participation.

Resumen

El control social constituye un mecanismo institucional para la participación comunitaria en la formulación e implementación de políticas de salud pública en Brasil. Los Consejos Locales de Salud (CLS) pueden ser instrumentos importantes para apoyar la gestión municipal y el proceso de descentralización del Sistema Único de Salud (SUS). Este trabajo tuvo como objetivo relatar la experiencia vivida, entre 2023 y 2024, por residentes de una Residencia Multidisciplinaria en Salud de la Familia en el proceso de reactivación del CLS, de una unidad de salud de la familia, ubicada en un municipio del interior de Bahía. Se trata de un estudio descriptivo, del tipo relato de experiencia. Las acciones realizadas, organizadas a través del diagnóstico situacional, planteadas por la planificación estratégica, brindaron condiciones para el diálogo sobre el control social y la participación popular, actuando como impulsores para el establecimiento del debate y la problematización del proceso de trabajo en la atención básica de salud, además de facilitar la restablecimiento del CLS en el municipio, movilizándolo a los usuarios y la comunidad, trabajadores que trabajan en los equipos y gestores de servicios.

Palabras Clave: Atención Primaria de Salud; Control Social; Consejos de Salud; Participación de la Comunidad.

Resumo

O controle social constitui mecanismo institucional de participação da comunidade na formulação e implementação das políticas públicas de saúde no Brasil. Os conselhos Locais de Saúde (CLS) podem ser instrumentos importantes para apoio à gestão municipal e para o processo de descentralização do Sistema Único de Saúde (SUS). Este trabalho teve como objetivo relatar a experiência vivenciada, entre 2023 e 2024, por residentes de uma Residência Multiprofissional em Saúde da Família no processo de reativação do CLS, de uma unidade de saúde da família, situada em um município do interior da Bahia. Trata-se de um estudo descritivo, do tipo relato de experiência. As ações realizadas, organizadas por meio de diagnóstico situacional, suscitado pelo planejamento estratégico, deram condição para o diálogo acerca do controle social e da participação popular, funcionando como propulsoras para o estabelecimento do debate e problematização do processo de trabalho na atenção básica de saúde, além de propiciar o restabelecimento dos CLS no município, mobilizando usuários e comunidade, trabalhadores atuantes nas equipes e gestores dos serviços.

Palavras-chave: Atenção Primária à Saúde; Controle Social; Conselhos de Saúde; Participação da comunidade.

Introduction

The process of redemocratization in Brazil and the enactment of the 1988 Constitution (Brazil, 1998), which established in article 198 that society should participate in the management of the health system, established the basis for the implementation of social participation in public health policies in the country. Social control in Health, regulated by laws 8,080 and 8,142, both in 1990, ensures that different

social segments, health professionals, managers, service providers, and, above all, users of the system, participate in the control of policies, monitoring implementation and proposing improvements to the actions and services offered (Brazil, 1990a; Brazil, 1990b).

In this sense, building possibilities to encourage the implementation of social control in the health field is extremely important for the defense of the Unified Health System (SUS) as a social and universal right, understanding that its sustainability, as was the case in its conception and creation, depends on the strength of the various social actors involved.

Health Councils and Conferences represent important strategic political spaces for social participation in the definition and implementation of health policies in the country. Despite advances throughout history, these bodies continue to face enormous challenges in consolidating the democratization of health actions in the SUS (Lisboa et al., 2016).

Health Councils are collegiate, deliberative, and permanent bodies of the SUS in each sphere of Government and are part of the organizational structure of the Ministry of Health, the Health Secretariat of the States, the Federal District, and the Municipalities (Brazil, 2012). However, despite the legal apparatus, Health Councils encounter difficulties in the effective capacity of influence and social control in the decision-making process and intervention in health policies (Van Stralen et al., 2006, Lisboa et al., 2016; Miwa; Serapioni; Ventura, 2017; Bortoli; Kovaleski, 2019).

Even so, some successful initiatives by Health Councils with real influences on local realities have been reported in the literature (Jerome, 2018; Bortoli; Kovaleski, 2019). A study carried out in Criciúma - SC, for example, found, based on the content of the resolutions of the Municipal Health Council (MHC) and the perception of the councilors interviewed, that the council's debates and decisions were able to effectively influence the production of public policies, improving access and the quality of care provided in the municipality. In this study, the councilors recognized the importance of strengthening ties between MHC and Local Health Councils (LHC) and listening to the population's concerns on a larger scale (Bortoli; Kovaleski, 2019).

LHCs can be necessary instruments to support municipal management and the decentralization process of the SUS. However, although Resolution No. 453/2012 (Brazil, 2012) mentions them, it does not provide specifications on their performance,

composition or scope, leaving it up to the municipalities to legislate on them (Miwa; Serapioni; Ventura, 2017). In other words, the functioning and development of LHCs are directly associated with the establishment of links between municipal and local authorities (Bortoli; Kovaleski, 2019, Lisboa et al., 2016).

An important issue highlighted by some studies (Machado et al., 2023; Miwa, Serapioni; Ventura, 2017; Lisboa et al., 2016; Quandt et al., 2013) is that simply establishing LHC does not seem to guarantee quality of performance and its effectiveness in decisions related to Primary Health Care actions/activities in its area of coverage. In addition, the performance of each LHC, even if it is in the same municipality, can be pretty different and dependent on the unique organization of each community (Buziquia et al., 2024).

A study carried out in the context of three Family Health Strategy (FHS) services in a municipality in southern Brazil, which had active LHC from 2019 to 2021, found that the experiences of each territory involved difficulties but also potential. In other words, despite different perspectives (professional, user, and manager) and distinct realities of each context, the interviewees' statements reiterated the importance of the formal LHC space as a way of maintaining a channel for voicing the community's interests and ensuring dialogue for collective decisions (Buziquia et al., 2024).

Another initiative to recognize effective changes enhanced by the LHC was reported by Jerome (2018) in Fortaleza - CE, who described in his study the report of a local council president regarding an organized action to facilitate the collection of medicines at bus stops, suggested by community residents, which ended up leading to the creation of a municipal program for dispensing medication at bus terminals.

Thus, making the LHC work as institutional instruments that allow the inclusion of the community in the formulation and monitoring of health policy, from each Family Health Unit (FHU) established in the territory, becomes a fundamental imperative, given the various problems faced by the SUS (Santos et al., 2020).

Furthermore, such councils, as they are instances of participation closer to the community, and therefore closer to the daily lives of users and the dynamics of health services, are strategic components of participatory management (Lisboa et al., 2016). This participatory dynamic strengthens the link between the population and health

services, contributing to the strengthening of Primary Health Care, as recommended by the Family Health Strategy, and the continuous improvement of strategies aimed at health promotion (Busana; Heidemann; Wendhausen, 2015).

However, some factors hinder the active participation of the population in LHC, such as lack of knowledge/misinformation, lack of dissemination (Miwa, Serapioni; Ventura, 2017; Cechinel et al., 2020), lack of adequate infrastructure and security in the territory (Cechinel et al., 2020), lack of connection between the LHC and the MHC (Quandt et al., 2013), clash between civil society and municipal government, informational and cognitive asymmetries between actors/advisors (Bortoli; Kovaleski, 2019) and discredit on the impact of councils on political decisions and interventions in local Health (Cechinel et al., 2020; Varela et al., 2020).

However, some studies report situations of Brazilian municipalities that managed to structure and maintain active LHC. Machado et al. (2023), for example, analyzing the performance and functioning of LHC in the city of Porto Alegre - RS, identified their creation in 2010 at the initiative of the MHC and the existence in 2018 of 56 active LHC in the universe of 126 Basic Health Units (BHU) in the municipality. The authors point out that despite the challenges faced, there seem to be local actors involved in their maintenance and that these spaces have some relevance for the BHU, as well as the existence of political will and the initiative of managers and governors is essential to legitimize and enhance actions to promote community participation in Health and its effects on decision-making processes involving public policies. Varela et al. (2020) reported on the experience of implementing the LHC in the municipality of Milagres, CE, highlighting the motivation of the FHS team for this initiative and the mobilization process that involved participation and fostered maturity in the group of counselors over time. According to the authors, the LHC involved initiatives that promoted Health and increased visibility of social needs in the area covered by the FHS involved.

In order to strengthen and encourage initiatives to structure LHC in the country, the National Health Council (NHC), through Resolution No. 714 of July 2, 2023, decided to develop a campaign for the creation of Local Health Councils in the Basic Health Units (BHU) of the SUS (Brazil, 2023). In 2023, the NHC launched the campaign "Here we have a Local Health Council" and, in 2024, the Guide for the Implementation of LHC in BHU, which appears to be a crucial national mobilization for the implementation and

expansion of these spaces (Brazil, 2024). Additionally, to strengthen transparency and participation in social control in the SUS, the NHC makes available to state, municipal, and district councils the Health Council Monitoring System (Siacs), a tool developed to gather all types of data from health councils, such as composition, organization, infrastructure, functioning, among others (Brazil, 2019).

Aware of this movement, a group from the Multiprofessional Residency in Family Health (ResMSF) at the State University of Feira de Santana (UEFS), which has as its field of practice a municipality in the interior of Bahia, visualized through a situational diagnosis, raised by the strategic planning carried out in activities of the ResMSF -UEFS program that the implementation of LHC was included as a goal in the municipal health plan, but none of them were active or held regular meetings.

This situation sparked interest in resuming implementation and regularizing LHC meetings. The process was initiated at a Family Health Unit (FHU), which serves as a teaching-work camp for residents, as the council had been inactive and had not met since the COVID-19 pandemic.

Given this interest, the possibility of working on the reconstruction of social control in the municipality was envisioned, taking into account its legal existence and, above all, its indispensability in the political sphere of defending Health as a social law.

It is worth noting that, in general terms, the academic training scenario of residents who participate in Multiprofessional Residency Programs in Health is not very different from the reality of undergraduate courses in the health area in the country that prioritize the performance of technical procedures, protocols, and conducts and barely include the topic of social participation (Silva et al., 2023; Buziquia et al., 2024). Furthermore, multidisciplinary work is rarely carried out in practical health activities during undergraduate courses, with a strong emphasis on individuality and competition to achieve professional success (Silva et al., 2023).

However, the activities developed by the ResMSF -UEFS program encourage the development of skills and practices aimed at comprehensive and multidisciplinary health care, as well as motivating the formation of critical, participatory subjects with an ethical-political commitment to defending an equitable and universal SUS, made for and with the participation of the community, as a political strategy for qualifying the health actions and services offered.

Thus, the objective of this work is to report the experience lived by residents of ResMSF -UEFS in the process of reactivating the LHC of a FHU located in a municipality in the interior of Bahia in the period between 2023 and 2024.

Methodology

This is a descriptive study that reports the experience of a multidisciplinary team of family health residents in collaboration with the Primary Health Care (PHC) team of a municipality in Bahia. The actions were planned and developed between 2023 and 2024, with meetings organized both at the FHU itself and in spaces reserved for collective activities.

The first stage of the process involved visualizing the problem related to LHC inactivity and utilizing situational diagnosis as a strategic planning tool. This identification occurred during activities of the disciplines "Family Health Strategy I and II" and in a situational strategic planning workshop promoted by the ResMSF -UEFS Program.

As an initial step, a meeting of the LHC of the FHU hub of ResMSF-UEFS was proposed and held, with the aim of understanding its functioning and identifying the leading actors involved prior to the COVID-19 pandemic. This meeting was attended by former board members, health professionals, and residents. Following this meeting, several additional actions were proposed to raise awareness among the community and family health professionals about the importance of implementing the LHC.

To raise awareness among the community and health professionals about the importance of the LHC, several outreach activities were conducted, including presentations in waiting rooms, operational groups, and the distribution of informational materials. A workshop was then organized on the theme "Social control through local health councils", aimed at primary care professionals in the municipality and users of the health service. The objective of this activity was to discuss the importance of social control and to plan the reactivation of the LHC collectively.

Based on the discussions and planning, periodic monthly meetings of the LHC were implemented at the aforementioned FHU. During these meetings, new council members were elected. Finally, unified LHC bylaws for the municipality were drafted.

These bylaws were collectively discussed and adjusted and will be presented for approval by the Municipal Health Council. This methodological process enabled the reactivation of the LHC in some FHUs within the municipality, involving the community and health professionals in the social control of health policies, thereby strengthening the SUS and promoting community participation.

Experience report

The process of reactivating the LHC at the FHU of ResMSF -UEFS began with the identification of weaknesses in social control through a situational health diagnosis. This analysis revealed that community ties weakened during the pandemic years, resulting in the inactivity of the previously established local council.

This weakness was identified during a strategic planning workshop, where residents used the problem tree tool as an analysis, diagnosis, and planning instrument, with the central problem being recognized as the "inactivity of the FHU Local Health Council in the post-COVID-19 pandemic period", as shown in Figure 1. This exercise enabled us to identify the causes of the LHC's inactivity, including a lack of incentive for popular participation by management, a lack of coordination between FHU and LHC representatives, and the limitations imposed by the pandemic.

The consequences of this inactivity were described as low population participation in social control decision-making processes, a lack of representation in the MHC, a lack of proposals for community health improvement, and a lack of population knowledge about the difficulties faced by the health service.

To address this situation, specific objectives were set, namely: raising awareness in the community and health professionals about the importance of participating in these deliberative bodies, such as councils; resuming LHC meetings; strengthening its actions and enabling the creation of a bond between users and the health team, aiming at a better understanding of the demands of the territory.

The planned actions included holding a discussion group on the topic of social control in Health, open to service professionals and the community; resuming regular meetings at the FHU hub; addressing issues related to social control in operational groups and waiting rooms; disseminating the dates of local council meetings to the community and participation in MHC meetings.

Figure 1: Strategic planning workshop with a presentation of the problem tree.

Source: Own authorship, 2023.

Strategic planning was essential in this process, enabling a clear visualization of the problem, its causes and consequences, and the structuring of more effective and contextualized actions for reactivating the LHC. This is because health planning aims to improve the performance of policies, actions, and services, functioning as an instrument that supports the recognition and systematization of problems in the territory, as well as the collective construction of solutions to these problems (Ferreira et al. 2017).

Although social control is legally instituted, its institutionalization does not guarantee effective participation (Lisboa et al., 2016; Miwa; Serapioni; Ventura, 2017; Bortoli; Kovaleski, 2019). There must be a liberating dialogue before and during the construction of the process, capable of encouraging people to fight for their citizenship rights.

In order to achieve social control and the incorporation of the population in this process, it is important to remember that the place of citizenship is where everything should be seen. It is essential to effectively share the information needed to understand the various situations involving the health needs of a given region, so that proposed solutions to the problems identified can be devised (Soratto; Witt; Faria, 2010).

A discussion group with professionals and the community was held for this purpose and was attended by 58 people, including users, representatives of residents' associations, residents, health workers, and managers, and lasted 8 hours. The first session was attended by a representative of the Popular Health Forum of the city of Feira de Santana-BA, who opened the meeting by presenting considerations related to the history of political struggle for the conception and construction of the SUS, as well as presenting the legal framework that provides for the existence of social control. In the second session, the participants were divided into subgroups, where strategies were discussed to make health councils visible and to mobilize the population and workers in this process, and the results of the group discussions were shared with everyone at the end.

Although the effects were not immediate, it was possible to notice a gradual increase in user interest and participation, especially as they began to understand the role of social control and the importance of their presence in deliberation spaces. Among professionals, the exchange of experiences also favored openness to participation and recognition of the LHC as a tool to support health work.

From this, possibilities were raised to strengthen and make the health councils visible in the municipality, namely: articulation with residents' associations, community groups, and leaders, with workers' unions and the student movement; introduction of the theme in the daily work process of primary health care workers; encouragement of participation in the councils by the municipal management; creation of internal regulations for the LHC of the respective family health units; intersectoral articulation, such as with the municipal education department, among others.

This activity was an essential mechanism for publicizing the Health Councils, including local and municipal ones, with the aim of highlighting their value for the health field and for the community in general. Furthermore, it served as a strategy to create possibilities for the visibility and functioning of citizen participation within the scope of municipal health policy.

Based on this approach, strategies were developed to ensure the effectiveness of the process, starting with a search for users willing to act as community representatives. During this search, it became apparent that users lacked motivation,

which made the acceptance process challenging. Oral presentations on the importance and functions of the LHC were given in the unit's waiting rooms, in operational groups, and in any other appropriate environments. For this purpose, some informative materials were used, as shown in Figure 2. The Community Health Agents (CHAs) engaged and committed to the process, aiming to ensure that at least one user represented each micro-area of the territory.

Figure 2: Information leaflet distributed to the population about Local Health Councils.

COMO POSSO PARTICIPAR?

Se informe se na unidade de saúde em que você trabalha ou é atendido possui um conselho local de saúde; (as reuniões são abertas à comunidade e qualquer pessoa pode participar);

Caso não tenha, você pode mobilizar a comunidade, procurar suporte de outros conselhos e/ou outros profissionais para construir um conselho local de saúde na sua unidade;

Podem ser feitas reuniões com a comunidade, associação de moradores, lideranças comunitárias para dialogar sobre os conselhos locais de saúde e promover a participação da população.

UNIDADES DE SAÚDE DA FAMÍLIA QUE POSSUEM CONSELHO LOCAL DE SAÚDE ATIVO EM SANTO ESTÊVÃO:

- USF CLÓVES PIRES;
- USF ANÍSIA CAROLINA (CABEÇA DA VACA);
- USF MARCELINO JÚLIO DE OLIVEIRA (CAATINGUINHA).

Conselho Local de Saúde

VOCÊ SABIA QUE SANTO ESTÊVÃO POSSUI CONSELHOS LOCAIS DE SAÚDE?

AFINAL, O QUE É UM CONSELHO LOCAL DE SAÚDE?

É um órgão deliberativo e consultivo, composto por representantes da comunidade, profissionais de saúde e gestores. Ele desempenha um papel fundamental na formulação de políticas, no acompanhamento e na avaliação das ações e dos serviços de saúde prestados em sua região.

PRINCIPAIS OBJETIVOS:

- ✓ **Promover a Participação da Comunidade**, envolvendo ativamente os cidadãos na tomada de decisões relacionadas à saúde local;
- ✓ **Monitorar e Avaliar os Serviços de Saúde**, incentivando a qualidade e a eficiência dos serviços de saúde em nossa comunidade;
- ✓ **Defender os Direitos dos Usuários**, assegurando que todos tenham acesso aos serviços de saúde de forma justa e igualitária.

POR QUE É IMPORTANTE A MINHA PARTICIPAÇÃO?

Ao participar ativamente, você possibilita que as necessidades e opiniões da comunidade sejam ouvidas e consideradas nas decisões relacionadas à saúde;

Sua participação ajuda a identificar problemas nos serviços de saúde e a propor soluções eficazes para melhorar o atendimento e a qualidade do cuidado prestado;

Participar ativamente do processo de tomada de decisões sobre a saúde é um exercício fundamental da cidadania, que fortalece nossa democracia e nosso compromisso com o bem-estar coletivo.

Source: Own authorship, 2023.

With the participation of users recruited through health education activities, the first meetings were held with the aim of raising awareness in the community and involving its members in the importance of reactivating the councils. Elections for new members were organized. However, significant challenges were faced, such as the lack of adequate infrastructure and the need to implement a policy of ongoing education for councilors since there was no prior knowledge about their role or functioning.

One of the most important activities was the preparation and presentation of a unified internal regulation at the MHC. This regulation aimed to ensure the effective functioning of the LHC in the municipality, providing clear and structured guidelines for their activities. The formalization of this document is a crucial step toward the institutionalization and sustainability of LHC actions, facilitating communication and integration between the municipal administration, LHC, and MHC, ensuring that they continue to play a vital role in promoting the health and well-being of the community.

During the process, some initial resistance was observed among managers and health professionals, particularly regarding the reorganization of work processes and the opening up of dialogue with the community. This resistance was partly related to a lack of knowledge about the role of the LHC and the existing overload in the teams' routines. However, as actions progressed and collective discussions were strengthened, it was possible to gain greater support and awareness among those involved. In addition, there were limitations such as a lack of availability of adequate spaces for council meetings, a lack of basic support materials, and a lack of human resources for mobilization and continuous monitoring of activities due to the turnover of professionals and precarious employment relationships. These obstacles reinforce the need for planning, institutional support, and public policies that guarantee the sustainability of participatory practices in the territory.

There are still numerous difficulties in the municipality, including low user participation and low engagement of workers and teams, partly justified by the fragility of labor relations and family health units without active local councils, which shows us the urgency of continuing to focus on this issue. These difficulties are also described in other Brazilian municipalities (Arantes; Shimizu; Merchán -Hamann, 2016).

Participation in the council requires ongoing financial investment and mobilization. Carrying out activities in the territories together with the communities, in residents' associations or workers' unions, youth groups, or even in places where there is a presence of collectives, such as churches and other social spaces, is essential to spread the discussion of social participation in the SUS and further increase the recognition of this space as legitimate and necessary.

Another vital measure to ensure the continuity of the LHC's operation is to maintain ongoing training for its members. During the period of the experience reported here, the residents carried out health education activities, emphasizing essential aspects in relation to social control in waiting room settings and as a topic in the health unit's operational group.

In corroboration with the studies of Bortoli and Kovaleski (2019) and Buziquia et al. (2024), we understand that to avoid a drop in participation, it is essential to keep the population mobilized and ensure that their demands are addressed in concrete ways. The perception that their voice is heard and considered strengthens the link with the social control spaces.

The following actions of the LHC, still underway, include granting autonomy to the conduct of meetings by their respective members, drafting a statute, approving the rules of procedure at the MHC, and resolving problems identified in the community. The mobilization and ongoing engagement of LHC members are essential for the consolidation of a participatory and democratic health system. The activities carried out to date demonstrate the transformative potential of popular participation in health management, highlighting the importance of initiatives that promote dialogue, collaboration, and collective action.

As professionals in training to work in the field of Primary Care, the experience of reactivating the local council of a FHU proved to be of great relevance in the training process of residents, given the opportunity to directly experience the process of social participation and develop skills and attitudes in the relationship with professionals and users of the service, which are essential for training and professional practice in the SUS. Thus, the interaction between professionals from the health teams, users of the service, and managers was fundamental to thinking about and articulating improvements in the participation of society in the formulation of health policies.

We hope that the socialization of the experience reported here, will generate a collective effort to reactivate the LHC in the municipality, based on the reality of a FHU pole in a municipality in Bahia, organized based on strategic planning and experiences of activities promoted by the ResMSF -UEFS program, will serve as a potential reference and inspiration for other initiatives to implement, implement or reactivate this critical form of social participation, which are the LHC, in other Brazilian municipalities. To this end, agreeing with Buziquia et al. (2024), we recommend that the LHC not be thought of as a bureaucratized institutional mechanism but that the realities and relational dynamics specific to each territory be considered.

Final Considerations

Social control, an institutional mechanism for the participation of different social segments in the formulation, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of public health policies, is essential for the defense of health as a social and citizenship law. In this regard, we emphasize the need for effective mobilization of the various social actors involved in the field of health and beyond to build a broad front in safeguarding an equitable and universal SUS. The LHC is a fundamental space in this process, as it enables the community to be heard, engage in debate over public policies, and develop collective solutions.

The joint mobilization of different social actors is crucial to the effectiveness of LHC. Each of these actors can contribute effectively based on their social role. For example, users and the community can bring demands and experiences from the territory, health workers can contribute their practical experiences, social movements can strengthen the fight for rights, and academic institutions have the potential to support this effort with training and research.

The actions carried out so far by the group of residents have enabled the expansion of the dialogue on social control and popular participation in health, acting as catalysts for reflection and debates on the ways of organizing work in primary care in the municipality, promoting an environment that is more sensitive to local demands and encouraging collective protagonism. This process has even driven the reestablishment

of other LHC, instigating the participation of users and the community, team workers, and service managers. However, the municipality needs to overcome challenges that still exist, such as low community participation, fragile employment relationships, and units without active councils. Furthermore, to ensure the long-term continuity of operation and effective performance of the LHC, more investment is needed in training counselors, mobilization of other FHS teams, institutional support, valorization of participation, and coordination with different bodies. Thus, we hope that the LHC can consolidate themselves as permanent instruments of social control and defense of the SUS in the municipality.

References

ARANTES, L. J.; SHIMIZU, H. E.; MERCHÁN-HAMANN, E. Contribuições e desafios da Estratégia Saúde da Família na Atenção Primária à Saúde no Brasil: revisão da literatura. **Ciência & Saúde Coletiva**, v.21, n.5, p.1499-1510, 2016. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-81232015215.19602015>

BORTOLI, F. R.; KOVALESKI, D. F. Efetividade da participação de um conselho municipal de saúde na região Sul do Brasil. **Saúde em debate**, v.43, n.123, p.1168-1180, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/0103-1104201912315>

BRASIL. **Conselho Local de Saúde**: Guia para a implementação nas Unidades Básicas de Saúde (UBS). Brasília, DF: Conselho Nacional de Saúde, 2024. Disponível em: <https://www.gov.br/conselho-nacional-de-saude/pt-br/aqui-tem-conselho-local-de-saude/CartilhaCNSConselhosLocaisdeSadeFinal02.09.pdf/view> Acesso em: 09 out. 2024.

BRASIL. **Resolução nº 453, de 10 de maio de 2012**. Brasília, DF: Conselho Nacional de Saúde, 2012. Disponível em: https://bvsms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/cns/2012/res0453_10_05_2012.html Acesso em: 09 out. 2024.

BRASIL. **Resolução nº 714, de 2 de julho de 2023**. Dispõe sobre Campanha pela Criação de Conselhos Locais de Saúde nas Unidades Básicas de Saúde do SUS. Brasília, DF: Conselho Nacional de Saúde, 2023. Disponível em: <https://www.gov.br/conselho-nacional-de-saude/pt-br/acao-a-informacao/legislacao/resolucoes/2023/resolucao-no-714.pdf/view> Acesso em: 09 out. 2024.

BRASIL. **Sistema de acompanhamento dos conselhos de saúde requer que municípios e estados atualizem informações**. Brasília, DF: Site do Conselho Nacional de Saúde, 2019. Disponível em: <https://www.gov.br/conselho-nacional-de-saude/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2019/abril/sistema-de-acompanhamento-dos-conselhos-de-saude-requer-que-municipios-e-estados-atualizem-informacoes> Acesso em: 09 out. 2024.

BRASIL. **Constituição (1988)**. Constituição da República Federativa do Brasil de 1988. Brasília, DF: Presidência da República, 1988. Disponível em: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/constituicao/constituicao.htm Acesso em: 09 out.2024

BRASIL. **Lei 8.142, de 28 de dezembro de 1990.** Dispõe sobre a participação da comunidade na gestão do Sistema Único de Saúde - SUS e sobre as transferências intergovernamentais de recursos financeiros na área da saúde e dá outras providências. Brasília, DF: Diário Oficial da União 1990b.

BRASIL. **Lei nº 8.080, de 19 de setembro de 1990.** Dispõe sobre as condições para a promoção, proteção e recuperação da saúde, a organização e o funcionamento dos serviços correspondentes e dá outras providências. Brasília, DF: Diário Oficial da União 1990a.

BRASIL. **Manual para entender o Controle Social.** Brasília, DF: Ministério da Saúde, 2014.

Disponível em:

https://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/para_entender_controle_social_saude.pdf Acesso em: 2 jul. 2024

BUSANA, J. A.; HEIDEMANN, I. T. S. B.; WENDHAUSEN, Á. L. P. Popular participation in a local health council: limits and potentials. **Texto & Contexto-Enfermagem**, v.24, n.2, p.442-449, 2015. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/0104-07072015000702014>

BUZQUIA, S. P.; GONÇALVES, T. R.; LOECK, J. F.; JUNGES, J. R. Experiências de participação social no contexto da Atenção Primária em Saúde: um estudo qualitativo. **Physis: Revista de Saúde Coletiva**, v.34, n.e34098, p.1-20, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0103-7331202434098pt>

CECHINEL, N. D. F. R.; FARIA, M. A. D.; RAMOS, A. R.; GIUGLIANI, C.; ROCHA, C. M. F. Participação social em saúde: limites e potencialidade de conselhos locais de saúde de uma metrópole brasileira. **Revista baiana de saúde pública**, v.44, n.3, p.56-71, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22278/2318-2660.2020.v44.n3.a2947>

FERREIRA, S. C. C.; SILVA, L. B.; MIYASHIRO, G. M. **Planejamento em saúde.** In: GONDIM, G. M. M.; CHRISTÓFARO, M. A. C.; MIYASHIRO, G. M. (Org.). Técnico de vigilância em saúde: fundamentos. v. 2. Rio de Janeiro: EPSJV, 2017. p. 137-164.

JEROME, J. S. Participatory governance in the context of local health councils: interviews with six local health council presidents in Northeastern Brazil. **Saúde e Sociedade**, v.27, n.3, p.740-753, 2018. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0104-12902018180226>

LISBOA, E. A.; SODRÉ F.; ARAÚJO, M. D.; QUINTANILHA, B. C., LUIZ, S. G. Conselhos locais de saúde: caminhos e (des) caminhos da participação social. **Trabalho, Educação e Saúde**, v.14, n.3, p.679-698, 2016. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1981-7746-sol00013>

MACHADO, F. V.; DOWBOR, M.W.; PINTO, R. S.; PEDROSO, V. D.; SENNA, F. S. F.; OLIVEIRA, A. K. et al. Desafios e potencialidades para a estruturação e o funcionamento dos Conselhos Locais de Saúde de Porto Alegre. **Saúde em Redes**, v.9, n.1, p.1-28, 2023. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18310/2446-4813.2023v9n1.4122>

MIWA, M. J.; SERAPIONI, M.; VENTURA, C. A. A. A presença invisível dos conselhos locais de saúde. **Saúde e Sociedade**, v.26, n.2, p.411-423, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0104-12902017170049>

QUANDT, F. L.; FANTIN, A. D.; OLIVEIRA, J. R.; KOVALESKI, D. F. Análise sobre a participação da comunidade nos Conselhos Locais de Saúde: caso do município de Pomerode-SC. **Saúde & Transformação Social/Health & Social Change**, v.4, n.3, p.83-90, 2013. Disponível em: <https://incubadora.periodicos.ufsc.br/index.php/saudeetransformacao/article/view/2491>

Cenas Educacionais, v.8, n.e22151, 2025.

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16614726>

SANTOS, C. L.; SANTOS, P. M.; PESSALI, H. F.; ROVER, A. J. Os conselhos de saúde e a publicização dos instrumentos de gestão do SUS: uma análise dos portais das capitais brasileiras. **Ciência & Saúde Coletiva**, v.25, n.11, p.4389-4399, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-812320202511.00042019>

SILVA, A. B. F. B.; BORGES, G. S. S.; CORREIA, Y. V. C.; PASSOS, V. A.; CARDOSO, T. M. P. B.; SOUZA, M. C. O cuidar, o olhar subjetivo e a interprofissionalidade: Perceptos e trilhas nos processos formativos de residentes em saúde. **Cenas Educacionais**, v.6, n.e18324, p.1-17, 2023. Disponível em: <https://www.revistas.uneb.br/index.php/cenaseducacionais/article/view/18324>

SORATTO, J.; WITT, R. R.; FARIA, E. M. Participação popular e controle social em saúde: desafios da Estratégia Saúde da Família. **Physis: Revista de Saúde Coletiva**, v.20, n.4, p.1227-1243, 2010. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0103-73312010000400009>

VAN STRALEN, C. J.; LIMA, Â. M. D. D.; FONSECA SOBRINHO, D. D.; SARAIVA, L. D. E. S.; VAN STRALEN, T. B. D. S.; BELISÁRIO, S. A. Conselhos de Saúde: efetividade do controle social em municípios de Goiás e Mato Grosso do Sul. **Ciência & Saúde Coletiva**, v.11, n.3, p.621-632, 2006. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1413-81232006000300011>

VARELA, L. D.; FAUSTINO, R. dos S.; FREITAS, C. H. A.; SAMPAIO, Y. P. C. C.; OLIVEIRA, R. S. de; PINTO, A. G. A., *et al.* Conselho local de saúde: implantação e dificuldades da formação na Estratégia Saúde da Família. **Revista Brasileira em Promoção da Saúde**, v.33, n.10908, p.1-11, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5020/18061230.2020.10908>